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Article

Synthesis and characterization of a targeted nanoniosome based on anti-CD44 antibody and investigation of its binding to breast cancer cells (MCF-7) and induction of apoptosis

Mahnoush Bahrapour 1,2 Ali Jebali 1,2,3*

1 Medical Genomics Research Center, Tehran Medical Sciences Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran. 2 Department of Nanobiomimetic, Faculty of Advanced Sciences and Technology, Tehran Medical Sciences, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran. 3 Department of Medical Nanotechnology, Faculty of Advanced Sciences and Technology, Tehran Medical Science, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran. **Corresponding author:** Email: alijebal2011@gmail.com

Abstract: Targeted nanoniosomes are novel structures for cancer treatment and many researchers are working on it. The aim of this study was to construct and characterize a vaccine containing anti-CD44 antibody based on nanoniosomes and to investigate their binding to breast cancer cells (MCF-7) and induction of apoptosis. After preparing anti-CD44 antibody, one ml of a 5 mg/ml solution was prepared from it, then one ml of a special nanoniosome synthesis kit with a concentration of 100 mg/ml was mixed with one ml of a 1% solution of FITC fluorescent dye and mixed vigorously for 5 minutes. Then the obtained mixture was centrifuged at high speed at 10,000 rpm and the supernatant was discarded and added to the precipitate of the prepared antibody solution and mixed vigorously again for 5 minutes. After washing the nanoniosomes, they were evaluated using a DLS device to determine the size range, a TEM microscope to examine its shape, and a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 280 nm to determine the loading rate. Then, the breast cancer cell line MCF-7 was prepared and cultured in RPMI1640 culture medium enriched with 10% FBS, and half a milliliter of nanoniosomes at concentrations of 100, 50, and 25 mg/ml were added to half a milliliter of the prepared cell suspension and incubated for 24 hours. After treating breast cancer cells with synthesized nanoniosomes, 50 microliters of the treated cells were examined under a fluorescent microscope and photographs were taken of the cells attached to the nanoniosomes. Also, apoptosis testing was performed using annexin and PI dyes by flow cytometry. This study showed that the synthesized nanoniosomes were spherical in shape and ranged in size from 85 to 180 nm with an average size of 132 nm, a DPI of 0.2, and a positive zeta potential of 30 mV. In group one, i.e., cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/mL, the highest number of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells was observed, and decreasing the nanoniosome concentration had a decreasing effect on the number of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells. Nanoniosomes without CD44 did not have much effect on the number of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells. Antibody alone (group 5) was also almost similar to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 25 mg/mL (group 3). The results of the binding and entry test in different groups also showed that in group one, i.e. cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml, the highest amount of stained and luminous cells (+++) was observed, and to a lesser extent, luminous cells were also seen in groups 2 and 3. It seems that nanoniosomes conjugated with anti-CD44 antibody have the ability to induce apoptosis, but it is suggested that the efficacy of this nanoparticle be proven in vitro and in vivo with other molecular tests.

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Introduction

Breast cancer (BC) is one of the most common causes of cancer-related death in women worldwide (1). Despite recent advances in diagnostic and treatment strategies, patients in remission may still experience recurrence and metastasis, which is a major cause of mortality among BC patients (2). BC is considered a heterogeneous disease with a range of subtypes and stages, leading to different treatment responses and disease-specific outcomes (3-4). Different subtypes of BC can be identified primarily by immunohistochemistry (IHC) (5) and gene expression profiling (6). Based on IHC/fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) profiling, BC can be classified and divided into ER-positive, HER2-positive, and BCER-positive, and BCER-neg triads based on the presence of estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) (4). Among the three immunohistochemical subtypes of BC, TNBC, which represents approximately 20% of all cases, is most associated with a poor prognosis and worse survival due to early metastasis to other organs and the lack of clinically targeted therapies (10-6). At the molecular level, gene expression profiles have defined five major subtypes of BC (10-18). Experimental evidence has shown that cancer stem cells (CSCs) are the driving force that leads to tumor progression, metastasis, and resistance to conventional therapy (15-22). CSCs, also called tumor-initiating cells (TICs), constitute only 0.1-1% of all tumor cells, a small but significant subpopulation of undifferentiated cells in tumors (23). This subpopulation of cells is capable of self-renewal and differentiation into various cell types, which leads to tumor formation and subsequent metastasis (24). In addition, recent studies have shown that the number of cells with tumorigenic potential, namely mesenchymal stem cells, determines tumor heterogeneity (25-27). CSCs have specific surface markers, such as CD133+, CD44+, CD24-, CD34+, CD29+, CD38-, CD166+, epithelial cell adhesion molecule (EpCAM), and Lin-, which enable these cells to be isolated by FACS or other methods (4). Since BCSCs were first identified in 2003 based on the expression of CD44 and CD24, various biomarkers for BCSCs have been identified in BC patient tumor samples, animal models, and cell lines, indicating the existence of a variety of BCSC subsets. Furthermore, different BC subtypes show variations in the proportion of different BCSC subsets, which correspond to different patient treatment responses and clinical outcomes. Al-Hajj and colleagues were the first to identify tumor-initiating CSCs using the cell surface markers CD44 and CD24. They showed that a small subpopulation of cells (on the order of 100 cells) with a CD44+/CD24-/lin- phenotype were able to generate tumors with similar heterogeneity to the original tumor in immunodeficient mice, whereas other tumor cells were unable to generate similar tumors in mice. Furthermore, single-cell suspensions of CD44+/CD24-/lin- cells from human BC cells can self-renew, proliferate extensively, form clonal mammospheres, and exhibit resistance to chemotherapy in an in vitro cell culture system. Later, aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 (ADLH1) was identified as a marker of normal and malignant human mammary stem cells and a predictor of poor patient outcomes (16). Additional markers to characterize BCSCs, such as ABCG2, CD133, CD49f, LGR5, SSEA-3, CD70, and PROCR, have been recently reported.

To date, the biomarkers consistently used to identify BCSC phenotypes are CD44, CD24, and ALDH1. Accumulating evidence has shown that BCSCs with ALDH1+ and CD44+/CD24-/low phenotypes are responsible for tumor initiation, progression, metastasis, and drug resistance. CD44 is a transmembrane cell surface glycoprotein that is involved in many cellular functions, including cell adhesion, proliferation, survival, and differentiation. Increased expression of CD44 in BCSCs maintains the pluripotency of the BCSC population. CD24 is a sialoprotein that promotes cell adhesion, proliferation, and metastasis. While low or absent CD24 expression is a characteristic of BCSCs, the generation of a CD24+ cell population from CD24-/low cells has been reported following radiation treatment, suggesting a role for this protein in radio- and chemoresistance in breast cancer cell lines (28). To date, available cancer preventive vaccines work by preventing viral infections. For example, there are two vaccines that prevent viral infections that have long-term consequences of chronic infection, including cancer. The hepatitis B vaccine prevents infection with hepatitis B virus (HBV), where chronic HBV infection leads to a high risk of progression to cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) (29–30). The field of “cancer vaccines,” which are not anti-infective vaccines, is devoted to the immunotherapy of established tumors. For treatment, dendritic cells (DC) stimulated with tumor antigen have shown efficacy, and DC-based vaccines represent a promising immunotherapy for cancers. Sipuleucel-T is a cancer vaccine made from autologous dendritic cells loaded with an engineered fusion protein of prostatic acid phosphatase (PAP) and granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF). Phase III studies suggest that treatment with Sipuleucel-T can increase median survival in patients with refractory prostate cancer (31). Many human malignancies are characterized by both quantitative and qualitative deficiencies in the immune system.

Immunotherapy therefore holds promise for cancer treatment and has shown a complementary role to traditional cancer therapies. Compared to surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy, immunotherapy has shown several advantages over traditional cancer therapy (32). Current immunological strategies for cancer treatment include vaccines, monoclonal antibodies, and cell therapies. However, despite encouraging preclinical studies in cancer immunotherapy, clinical responses are limited to a limited patient population. There is increasing evidence that tumors contain a distinct subpopulation of stem cells (CSCs) (33–35). Recent studies have described several biomarkers for cancer stem cells. CD44+/CD24- for breast cancer, CD133+ for brain tumors, and CRC are resistant to traditional chemotherapy and radiotherapy and have been shown to be responsible for the initiation, recurrence, and metastasis of cancer cells. Protective antitumor immunity induced by ALDEFLUOR+/ALDH cancer stem cell-dendritic cell (CSC-DC) vaccine has been reported using histologically distinct murine tumor models that are immunocompatible with various hosts. ALDEFLUOR+/ALDH enriched cancer stem cells were immunogenic and served as a source of antigen in inducing protective antitumor immunity. The inability to target cancer stem cells with current immunological approaches may be a major factor in treatment failure (36).

The aim of this study was to construct and characterize a nanoniosome-based anti-CD44 antibody vaccine and to investigate its binding to breast cancer cells and induction of apoptosis.

Materials and methods

Summary of the work process

After purchasing the anti-CD44 protein antibody, one ml of a 5 mg/ml solution was prepared from it, then one ml of a special nanoniosome synthesis kit with a concentration of 100 mg/ml was mixed with one ml of a 1% solution of the fluorescent dye FITC and mixed vigorously for 5 minutes. Then the resulting mixture was centrifuged at high speed at 10,000 rpm and the supernatant was discarded and added to the precipitate of the prepared antibody solution and mixed vigorously again for 5 minutes. After washing with physiological serum, the final suspension obtained was evaluated using a DLS device to determine the size range and with a TEM microscope to examine its shape and with a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 280 nm to determine the loading rate. For the loading test, after centrifugation, the supernatant containing the unreacted antibodies was sampled and the optical absorption was read with a spectrophotometer or nanodrop at a wavelength of 280 nm and calculated according to the loading control. Then, the breast cancer cell line (MCF-7) was prepared and cultured in RPMI1640 culture medium enriched with 10% FBS, and half a milliliter of the cell suspension prepared with a density of one million cells/ml was added to half a milliliter of nanoniosomes at concentrations of 100, 50, and 25 mg/ml and incubated for 24 hours. In the control group, the cells used were not exposed to nanoniosomes and were treated with PBS. To investigate the binding of synthesized nanoniosomes to cancer cells, after treating breast cancer cells with synthesized nanoniosomes, 50 microliters of the treated cells were examined under a fluorescent microscope and photographs were taken of the cells. The control sample will consist of breast cancer cells treated with PBS. To investigate the induction of apoptosis in cancer cells after treatment, breast cancer cell line (MCF-7) is cultured in RPMI1640 culture medium enriched with 10% FBS and then a cell suspension is prepared and nanoniosomes are added to it at the above concentrations and after 24-hour incubation, apoptosis test is performed using annexin and PI dye by flow cytometry.

Synthesis of nanoniosomes conjugated with anti-CD44 antibody

After preparing anti-CD44 protein antibody in powder form, two ml of distilled water is added to it and mixed vigorously by hand for one minute and then mixed on a mixer for 5 minutes. Then 50 microliters of this solution is sampled and the optical absorbance is read with a nanodrop device at a wavelength of 280 nm. Then, one ml of the nanoniosome synthesis kit, one ml of carboxy-PEG and one ml of 1% FITC fluorescent dye solution were poured into a falcon and mixed by hand for one minute and then on a mixer for 5 minutes. Then, the resulting mixture was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 5 minutes. Then, the supernatant was completely discarded and one ml of the prepared antibody solution was added to the sediment and one ml of EDC solution was added and mixed vigorously on the mixer for 5 minutes. Then, it was incubated for half an hour at 37 degrees. Then, the resulting mixture was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 5 minutes. Then, 50 microliters of the supernatant were sampled and the optical absorption was read with a Nanodrop device at a wavelength of 280 nm.

The remaining supernatant was completely discarded and 3 ml of physiological serum was added to the sediment and mixed vigorously again for 5 minutes on a mixer. To determine the concentration of synthesized nanoparticles, first a small piece of Whatman filter was weighed and the scale was zeroed, then 100 microliters of synthesized nanoparticles were poured onto it and after one minute the weight of the dry mass was recorded. To ensure the formation of nanoliposomes, three characterization tests were considered for them: to determine the particle distribution using the DLS method, to determine the shape using the TEM microscope, and to prove conjugation using the FTIR method. For this, three microtubes were taken and 100 microliters of synthesized nanoparticles were poured into each, labeled, and sent to Dipetronic Company.

Cell culture and exposure to nanoparticles

First, 10 ml of RPMI1640 culture medium was added to the culture flask (T25) of breast cancer cells obtained from the Pasteur Institute, and the cells were removed by rapid pipetting with a 10 ml syringe, and finally a cell suspension with a density of one million cells/ml was prepared from it. One ml of the cell suspension was poured into a 24-well microplate, and after 24 hours of incubation at 37 degrees, one ml of nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml was added to it, and it was incubated again at 37 degrees for 24 hours. Exactly the same as the above step was performed for concentrations of 50 and 25 mg/ml.

Study groups

Cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group1).

Cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 50 mg/ml (Group2).

Cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 25 mg/ml (Group3).

Cancer cells not exposed to nanoniosomes and treated with normal saline instead (Group4).

Cancer cells exposed to anti-CD44 antibodies at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group5).

Cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes without anti-CD44 antibodies at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group6).

Apoptosis tests

After treating breast cancer cells with synthesized nanoniosomes, the cells were again removed by high-pressure pipetting and 50 μ l of each sample was poured onto a slide, dried at room temperature, and then fixed with a drop of methanol. Finally, the slides were examined under a fluorescent microscope, and the cells were photographed, and the number of stained cells in each microscopic plane was observed and finally summarized qualitatively in a table. Also, 100 μ l of each well was poured into a 2 ml microtube and sent to Dipetronic Company to determine the level of apoptosis of the exposed cells using Annexin and PI dyes by flow cytometry.

Results

The nanoniosomes characterization

Figure 1 shows a photograph of synthesized nanoniosomes with a TEM microscope and **Figure 2** shows the result of DLS test of synthesized nanoniosomes. In terms of shape, the nanoniosomes were spherical and in terms of size range they were in the range of 85 to 180 nm with an average size of 132 nm and DPI of 0.2. The zeta potential of synthesized nanoliposomes was also positive 30 mV. The antibody loading rate on nanoniosomes was also calculated to be about 87%. In the FTIR test, it was also determined that the absorption peaks of the anti-CD44 antibody were at the wave numbers of 1800-1600 cm^{-1} , 1570-1470 cm^{-1} , and 1350-1250 cm^{-1} , and the absorption peaks of the nanoniosomes without antibody were at 801 cm^{-1} , 1355 cm^{-1} , 1740 cm^{-1} , 2852 cm^{-1} , and 2943 cm^{-1} . Also, the absorption peaks of the nanoniosomes containing the antibody were at the wave numbers of 1800-1600 cm^{-1} , 1570-1470 cm^{-1} , 1350-1250 cm^{-1} , 801 cm^{-1} , 1355 cm^{-1} , 1740 cm^{-1} , and 2852 cm^{-1} , which was the sum of the absorption peaks of the antibody and nanoniosomes, indicating the binding of the antibody on the nanoparticle surface.

Figure 1. The photograph of synthesized nanoniosomes with a TEM microscope

Cumulant Operations

Size distribution	: 85-180nm
Z-Average	: 132nm
DPI	: 0.2
Zeta Average	: +30mV

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Figure 2. The DLS test result of synthesized nanoniosomes

Apoptosis Test Results

Table 1 shows the results of the apoptosis test as a numerical average in the different groups studied. What is clear is that in group one, i.e., cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml, the highest number of apoptotic and pre-apoptotic cells was observed. Reducing the nanoniosome concentration had a decreasing effect on the number of apoptotic and pre-apoptotic cells. We found that nanoniosomes without CD44 did not have much effect on the number of apoptotic and pre-apoptotic cells. The antibody alone (group 5) was also almost similar to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 25 mg/ml (group 3). **Figure 3** shows the results of the apoptosis test in the different groups studied. As is also clear here, in group one (A), i.e. cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml, the highest number of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells was observed, and decreasing the nanoniosome concentration had a decreasing effect on the number of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells. The effect of the antibody alone (E) was also almost similar to that of nanoniosomes at a concentration of 25 mg/ml (C). It is also clear in this graph that nanoniosomes without CD44 did not have much effect on the number of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells. **Figure 4** also shows the results of the apoptosis test in a graph in terms of cell types in the different groups studied. In terms of the amount of apoptotic cells (A), it can be said that the highest amount was observed in cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml, and decreasing the nanoniosome concentration showed its decreasing effect. In terms of the amount of peri-apoptotic (B) and necrotic (C) cells, it can be said that no significant difference was observed between the different groups. In terms of the amount of live cells (D), it can be said that cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml had the lowest amount of live cells, and with decreasing the nanoniosome concentration, an increase in live cells occurred.

Table 1. Apoptotic test results as a numerical average in the different groups studied. Cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group1), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 50 mg/ml (Group2), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 25 mg/ml (Group3), cancer cells not exposed to nanoniosomes and treated with normal saline instead (Group4), cancer cells exposed to anti-CD44 antibodies at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group5), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes without anti-CD44 antibodies at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group6).

	Apototic %	Pre-Apototic%	Necrotic %	Live %
Group 1	72	13	11	4
Group 2	64	12	10	14
Group 3	23	8	7	62
Group 4	8	5	5	82
Group 5	25	10	7	58
Group 6	9	6	8	77

Figure 3. Results of apoptosis test in different study groups. Cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (A), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 50 mg/ml (B), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 25 mg/ml (C), cancer cells not exposed to nanoniosomes and treated with normal saline instead (D), cancer cells exposed to anti-CD44 antibodies at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (E), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes without anti-CD44 antibodies at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (F). a means significant compared to other groups ($P < 0.05$) and b means significant compared to the amount of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells ($P < 0.05$)

Figure 4. Results of apoptosis test in terms of apoptotic (A), peri-apoptotic (B), necrotic (C) and viable cells (D) in different groups studied. Cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group1), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 50 mg/ml (Group2), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 25 mg/ml (Group3), cancer cells not exposed to nanoniosomes and treated with normal saline instead (Group4), cancer cells exposed to anti-CD44 antibodies at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group5), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes without anti-CD44 antibodies at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group6). a means there is a significant difference compared to other groups ($P < 0.05$) and

Binding test

Table 2 shows the qualitative results of the binding and entry test in the different groups studied. In group one, i.e. cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml, the highest number of stained and luminous cells (+++) was observed, and to a lesser extent, luminous cells were also seen in groups 2 and 3. In the size groups, stained and luminous cells were not seen under a fluorescent microscope. Photo 4-5 shows a sample of cells after 24-hour exposure to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml.

Table 2. Qualitative results of the binding and entry test in the different groups studied. Cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group1), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 50 mg/ml (Group2), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 25 mg/ml (Group3), cancer cells not exposed to nanoniosomes and treated with normal saline instead (Group4), cancer cells exposed to anti-CD44 antibodies at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group5), cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes without anti-CD44 antibodies at a concentration of 100 mg/ml (Group6).

	Stained cell count
Group 1	+++
Group 2	+
Group 3	+
Group 4	-
Group 5	-
Group 6	-

Discussion

The aim of this study was to construct and characterize a vaccine containing anti-CD44 antibody based on nanoniosomes and to investigate their binding to breast cancer cells (MCF-7) and induction of apoptosis. After synthesis and characterization by TEM and DLS, we found that the synthesized nanoniosomes were spherical in shape and had a size range of 85 to 180 nm with an average size of 132 nm and a DPI of 0.2. The zeta potential of the synthesized nanoliposomes was also positive 30 mV. The results of the apoptosis test in the different groups studied also showed that in group one, i.e. cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml, the highest number of apoptotic and pre-apoptotic cells was observed, and decreasing the nanoniosome concentration had a decreasing effect on the number of apoptotic and pre-apoptotic cells. We found that nanoniosomes without CD44 had no significant effect on the number of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells. Antibody alone (group 5) was also almost similar to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 25 mg/ml (group 3). In terms of the number of apoptotic cells (A), it can be said that the highest number was observed in cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes conjugated to CD44 at a concentration of 100 mg/ml, and decreasing the nanoniosome concentration showed a decreasing effect. In terms of the number of peri-apoptotic (B) and necrotic (C) cells, it can be said that no significant difference was observed between the different groups. In terms of the number of viable cells (D), it can also be said that cancer cells exposed to nanoniosomes conjugated to CD44 at a concentration of 100 mg/ml had the lowest number of viable cells, and with decreasing the nanoniosome concentration, the number of viable cells increased.

The results of the binding and entry test in different groups also showed that in group 1, i.e., cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml, the highest amount of stained and luminous cells was observed, and to a lesser extent, luminous cells were also observed in groups 2 and 3. In the size groups, stained and luminous cells were not observed under a fluorescent microscope. Some related studies are presented in this section. Guo et al. in 2020 showed that MUC1 may be required for CCSC vaccine to exert tumor immunity. CD133+CCSCs were isolated from the CT26 cell line using a magnetically activated cell sorting system, and MUC1 shRNA or recombinant plasmid was further used to reduce or increase MUC1 expression in CD133+CCSCs. Mice were immunized subcutaneously with CCSC lysates, MUC1 knockin CCSCs, and MUC1 knockdown CCSCs, respectively, followed by a challenge with CT26 cells. We found that the CCSC vaccine significantly reduced tumor growth through targeted killing of CCSCs, as evidenced by the reduction of CD133+ cells and ALDH+ cells in tumors. In addition, the CCSC vaccine significantly increased the cytotoxicity of NK cells and spleen cells, induced the release of IFN- γ , perforin, and granzyme B, and also reduced the expression of TGF- β 1. Furthermore, CCSC vaccination increased antibody production and reduced myeloid-derived suppressor cells and Treg subsets. More importantly, MUC1 knockdown partially impaired the antitumor efficacy of the CCSC vaccine, whereas MUC1 overexpression dramatically enhanced the safety of the CCSC vaccine. Overall, these results suggest a novel role and molecular mechanisms of MUC1 in CCSC vaccine against colorectal cancer (43). Wu et al. (2015) demonstrated that various immunotherapies for ovarian cancer may overcome the barriers of resistance to standard chemotherapy. Vaccine immunotherapy may be a useful adjunct to conditional chemotherapy regimens. The present study investigated the use of ovarian cancer stem cell (CSC) vaccines to inhibit ovarian cancer growth. CD117+CD44+CSCs were isolated from the human epithelial ovarian cancer (EOC) SKOV3 cell line using a magnetically activated cell sorting system. Pre-inactivated CD117+CD44+CSCs were vaccinated three times into athymic nude mice, and then the mice were challenged subcutaneously with SKOV3 cells. The antitumor efficacy of the CSC vaccine was evaluated by *in vivo* tumorigenicity, efficient immunoassay by flow cytometry, and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, respectively. The CD117+CD44+CSC vaccine enhanced the anti-ovarian cancer efficacy by reducing ovarian cancer growth in athymic nude mice. Vaccination resulted in increased serum IFN- γ , decreased TGF- β levels, and increased cytotoxic activity of natural killer cells in mice vaccinated with the CD117+CD44+CSC vaccine. Furthermore, the CSC-based vaccine significantly reduced CD117+CD44+CSC as well as aldehyde dehydrogenase 1-positive cell populations in ovarian cancer tissues in xenografted mice (44). Xu et al. (2023) investigated the immunogenicity of cancer stem cell (CSC) vaccines. Cancer stem cells were selected from mouse OC ID8 cells by serum-free culture. CSC vaccines were prepared by freezing and thawing these CSCs, and then injected into mice and then challenged with various OC cells. The *in vivo* antitumor effect of CSC immunization showed that the vaccines were able to induce significant immune responses to autologous tumor antigens in vaccinated mice, as the mice significantly inhibited tumor growth, prolonged survival, and decreased CSC numbers in OC tissues compared with mice without CSC vaccination.

In vitro immunohistochemistry of immunocytes against SKOV3, HO8910, and ID8 cells showed a significant killing effect compared with the control group. However, the antitumor effect was significantly reduced while the expression of mucin-1 in CSC vaccines was reduced by small interfering RNA. Overall, the findings of this study provided evidence that deepened our understanding of CSC vaccine immunogenicity and anti-OC efficacy, especially for the role of the dominant antigen mucin-1. It is possible to translate CSC vaccine into an immunotherapeutic approach against ovarian cancer (45).

Liu et al. (2021) evaluated the expression of programmed cell death ligand-1 (PD-L1) in colorectal CSCs (CCSCs) and non-CCSCs and designed a combination immunotherapy using PD-L1-CAR-T cells together with CCSC-DC simultaneously. Vaccine-sensitized T cells for colorectal cancer treatment PD-L1-CAR-T cells specifically recognized the PD-L1 molecule on CCSCs by binding to the extracellular domain of programmed cell death-1. The CCSC-DC vaccine was prepared using CCSC lysates. We found that aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 (ALDH1)-positive CCSCs were abundant in patient tumor tissue samples and cancer cell lines. Furthermore, PD-L1 was highly expressed in ALDH1-positive CCSCs compared with non-CCSCs. Monotherapy with PD-L1-CAR-T cells or the CCSC-DC vaccine only induced modest tumor regression *in vitro* and *in vivo*. However, combination therapy significantly eliminated cancer cells and reduced tumor burden in mice. Our findings may provide a novel strategy for the clinical treatment of colorectal malignancies (46).

Nanocarrier systems have been developed to overcome the limitations associated with hepatic first-pass metabolism in conventional oral dosage forms and the inhibitory properties of the lipid bilayer in the stratum corneum via transdermal drug delivery to improve the bioavailability of various drugs. In recent years, several vesicular targeted drug carriers such as liposomes, niosomes, proniosomes, transferosomes, autosomes, and electrosomes are under development. Among them, niosomes and proniosomes should be better carriers to enhance therapeutic efficacy and bioavailability with reduced side effects and act as a promising approach for transdermal drug delivery. Both are surfactant-based non-ionic vesicles and are amphiphilic. This article briefly reviews the possible mechanisms within niosomes and proniosomes to enhance drug delivery through the skin, their types, composition, preparation techniques, properties, and applications. According to the research conducted in the formulation of various nanocarrier systems through the transdermal approach to increase bioavailability, it can be stated that the first-pass metabolism in the liver can be reduced and the therapeutic efficiency can be increased several times compared to them. Oral formulations in the market The phenomenon of targeting drug delivery systems is to deliver the drug in the body in such a way that in order to achieve a therapeutic response, it must show its action to the desired site, that is, where it should act by limiting undesirable interactions to non-necessary ones. -Targeted tissues Paul Ehrlich proposed this idea in 1909 and called this strategy "magic bullets". In drug delivery system, although oral route of administration is useful but it is limited due to first pass hepatic metabolism which increases undesirable side effects, reduces therapeutic efficacy and bioavailability of many drugs in treatment of various diseases.

Hence, transdermal drug delivery system offers an attractive, non-invasive and better alternative method to reduce the number of doses, frequency of administration, systemic toxicity, first pass hepatic metabolism, gastric irritation, oral related unwanted side effects, control the drug level in plasma for a sustained period locally and systemically which leads to increased bioavailability and better patient compliance. However, the lipid bilayer of skin which is stratum corneum acts as a very tough diffusion barrier and limits the penetration of active drug moieties. New approaches such as nanotechnology have been developed in the field of science, which has introduced new vesicular drug carrier systems such as liposomes, niosomes, proniosomes, autosomes and electrosomes. Among them, niosomes and proniosomes have distinct advantages over other vesicles by acting as drug-containing reservoirs. Liposomes are not preferred because they are composed of concentric phospholipids, which make the vesicles chemically unstable due to oxidative degradation and acidification. Niosomes are microscopic lamellar structures in an emerging drug delivery system composed of nonionic alkyl ether surfactant or polyglycerol and cholesterol in an aqueous medium. Handjani-Villa et al. introduced the class of niosomes.

These are amphiphilic, biocompatible, biodegradable and non-toxic materials for encapsulating drugs in vesicles that improve drug bioavailability, therapeutic efficacy, drug penetration through the skin, release the drug in a sustained and controlled manner and are used for targeting the drug. The desired site by adjusting the composition which helps in reducing side effects. However, the major drawback is the physical instability during storage which causes aggregation, fusion, sedimentation and leakage of the entrapped drug. This led to the development of a revolutionary technique of proniosomal system called "proniosomes". Proniosomes are hybrid niosomal particles of compressed or dry liquid crystalline carrier particles coated with non-ionic surfactants and immediately converted into niosomal dispersions with hot water by gentle agitation before use. These versatile vesicular carriers represent a more promising approach for transdermal drug delivery and act as vehicles or penetration enhancers through the stratum corneum. These vesicles are preferred and well documented because they exhibit excellent physical and chemical stability, non-toxicity, biodegradable, biocompatible, skin penetration ability, prolonged drug release, increased bioavailability and reduced side effects and high reflux. Most of the research initiators agreed that effective drug delivery is achieved through direct contact of these vesicles with the skin. An important requirement for transdermal delivery is that the drug carried by the vehicle should be able to reach the skin surface at a sufficient rate and in sufficient quantity. A wide range of applications and numerous mechanisms have been reported due to their ability to enhance drug transport through the skin to the deeper layer of the skin. In general, a penetrant applied to the skin has three possible routes across the epidermis. The intercellular route, a lipid domain associated with proteins within the cornea, the intercellular route, and the appendicular route, through hair follicles, through associated sebaceous glands and sweat ducts. Based on the nature of the drug, the mechanism of drug transport may vary. The mechanisms of skin enhancement of hydrophilic drugs include (1) increased thermodynamic activity of the drug - encapsulated drug vesicles are adsorbed and melt on the skin surface. Then, a thermodynamic activity gradient is created, which increases the diffusion pressure for drug penetration across the surface (48-50).

From this study, it can be concluded that the synthesized nanoniosomes were spherical in shape and ranged in size from 85 to 180 nm with an average size of 132 nm, a DPI of 0.2, and a positive zeta potential of 30 mV. In group one, i.e., cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/mL, the highest number of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells was observed, and decreasing the nanoniosome concentration had a decreasing effect on the number of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells. Nanoniosomes without CD44 did not have much effect on the number of apoptotic and peri-apoptotic cells. Antibody alone (group 5) was also almost similar to nanoniosomes at a concentration of 25 mg/mL (group 3). The results of the binding and entry test in different groups also showed that in group one, i.e. cancer cells exposed to CD44-conjugated nanoniosomes at a concentration of 100 mg/ml, the highest amount of stained and luminous cells (+++) was observed, and to a lesser extent, luminous cells were also seen in groups 2 and 3. It is suggested that the efficacy of this nanoparticle be proven in vitro with other molecular tests. It is suggested that the efficacy of this nanoparticle be checked in an animal model of cancer.

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